

DISTANCE LEARNING OF ENGLISH

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Abstract: Distance learning is increasingly being introduced into the educational process. Therefore, the search for innovations in the development of methods and technologies for such classes is considered a priority. In particular, scientists work in such areas: increasing the intensity of classes; expansion of content; building individual trajectories for each student, taking into account his abilities and the motivational and value sphere of personality; intensification of students' independent work. Although distance learning has appeared relatively recently, it has already become a serious educational element, has proven itself as a promising pedagogical technology. This type of class is gaining popularity due to the personal approach, taking into account the student's self-esteem, motivating him and using the latest technological tools in the training process.

Keywords: English; training; remotely; teaching; Internet; foreign; language. Positive aspects of teaching English remotely.

Аннотация: Дистанционное обучение все чаще внедряется в учебный процесс. Поэтому поиск нововведений в разработке методов и технологий для таких классов считается приоритетным. В частности, ученые работают в таких направлениях: повышение интенсивности занятий; расширение контента; построение индивидуальных траекторий для каждого ученика с учетом его способностей и мотивационно-ценностной сферы личности; активизация самостоятельной работы студентов. Хотя дистанционное обучение появилось сравнительно недавно, оно уже стало серьезным образовательным элементом, зарекомендовало себя как перспективная педагогическая технология. Этот вид занятий набирает популярность за счет индивидуального подхода, учета самооценки ученика, его мотивации и использования новейших технологических инструментов в процессе обучения.

Ключевые слова: английский; обучение; удаленно; обучение; Интернет; иностранный; язык, положительные стороны.

INTRODUCTION

If a few years ago, distance learning involved sending training materials

through mail, now, thanks to the development of technology, this process takes place through the Internet, through e-mail or through Skype. This approach has many positive aspects, the main of which is the ability of the student to engage at a convenient time for him anywhere where there is access to the network. Naturally, the teacher's work schedule should also be taken into account, but you can always agree with him and somehow adjust your plans. But, in any case, doing at home for a cup of hot tea, you can remember and learn everything much better than in the classrooms of the training center.

REFERENCES AND METHODS

The research process used the methods of objectivity, logic, analysis and synthesis of scientific knowledge. In the course of this research, the importance of Bloom's taxonomy was objectively revealed.

Possible difficulties in distance learning English.

First of all, we are talking about purely technical reasons for the disruption of the educational process, - computer breakdown, camera, interruptions in Internet communications and the like. These problems are solved by remote training service providers through alternative telephone communication, postponement of classes, their duration, and so on.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

What's new about remote learning technology developers?

1) Holding webinars, - interactive lectures, lasting from two to ten minutes, into which course theoretical material is divided. Their main feature is tests conducted at the end of the lesson, quizzes or control surveys that reveal the level of understanding of well-read information. Such lectures are most often broadcast in recordings.

2) Application of the "Khanovsky" method of information supply using a graphic tablet. Its peculiarity lies in voice reading and parallel drawing of explanatory diagrams, graphs and illustrations. In this, it is easy to see the spiral path of the development of science, which was widely studied during the Soviet Union, since the "Cretaceous" period of teaching with the help of chalk, plaque and the voice of the teacher transferred to the face in electronic form.

3) Submission of additional theoretical material in the form of links to sources on the Internet or a more advanced - multimedia method.

4) Workshops are various types of classes, both with native speakers and in the form of virtual interlocutors.

5) Automated checks of the results of completed tasks, since each teacher sometimes has such a number of students that he is not physically able

to process the entire flow of information.

6) Students are involved in independent, as well as mutual, cross-assessment of work.

7) Online discussions are held in thematic forums. They should be considered as places where students can help each other and ask questions, express their personal attitude to a particular course, receive support and encouragement for their achievements, receive information about the course, form educational groups and even organize meetings in real life if desired.

8) Great attention is paid to the cooperation of students among themselves, question and answer forums are organized. The key point of cooperation is to improve the quality of training by explaining incomprehensible points by students to each other. After all, the lively communication of interested persons makes it possible to quickly fill the gaps that arose for one reason or another in the information they received. Joint viewing and discussion of lectures is encouraged, as well as the search for answers to tasks set in quizzes.

As a rule, the founders of large projects of distance learning in English the language conducts serious research work, taking into account, among other things, also information received in specialized forums from customer feedback. Such studies provide an opportunity not only to assess the quality of information services and innovations promoted to the market, but also to improve their training in a timely manner.

Based on the studies already carried out, the following conclusions were drawn:

1) Lectures, the basis of the theoretical course of classes, are quite competitive with webinars, provided that they are enriched by communication between students, discretization and control. Also recognized as ineffective, often used in the Russian Federation long one and a half hour lectures.

2) A further problem of the online courses is the numerous, unjustifiable serious reasons, concessions provided by teachers to students in terms of the observance of the temporary lecture regime, due to which its effectiveness is significantly reduced. The solution in this case can only be a clear observance of the schedule of classes.

3) Educational institutions that offer distance learning courses in our country underestimate the importance of automation of knowledge testing, as well as self and mutual testing of knowledge by students. Too much emphasis should be placed on the independence of training. And cooperation, at least

minimal, between students gives a very tangible result.

Foreign distance learning courses pay great attention to the communication of students with each other in thematic forums and on social networks, which has a positive impact on the result of training. Such techniques should also be used in English courses.

What are the problems of full-time English instruction in educational institutions?

The current practice of full-time teaching of English in Uzbekistan suffers from a number of problems. This is another reason for those wishing to learn a foreign language using remote methods. What are these problems and are distance courses completely devoid of these shortcomings?

- 1) Current methodologies are not optimal. The time and effort that is spent on each student is quite great, but even in the case of high teacher qualification and division of the group into several subgroups, the results of training cannot be called optimal.
- 2) Insufficient intensity of colloquial preparation of students.
- 3) Poor basic preparation and too fast transition from reproductive work to productive work.
- 4) The negative impact of various kinds of long breaks in training, leading to the forgetting of material previously learned.
- 5) Lack of recommendations that are sufficiently productive to address and prevent deficiencies in the acquisition of knowledge and conversational skills among students.
- 6) A lot of gaps in the work of the student knowledge assessment system.
- 7) Unsatisfactory selection of visual aids and low didactic effect of their application.

Remote learning of English, by using the Internet, as a method of realizing the information rights of all participants in this process.

The information rights and obligations of students are generally not in conflict with each other. Even on the contrary, they complement each other in implementation. Learning English and self-education are a single continuous process of information saturation. The advantage of the information right over the obligation implies freedom of access to any educational materials, not controlled and not determined by the requirements of the educational system. If the information duty prevails in the learning process, then the personal information environment of the student is significantly narrowed and stops at such a level of development that meets the minimum mandatory requirements.

Further narrowing of the environment can lead to methodological and technological depletion of the educational process, due to the severance of connections between objects and closure in a very limited information space. As a result, a significant decrease in the effectiveness of classes can be observed.

Therefore, access to information cannot be limited to any framework, each of the educational actors should be able to use the entire volume of information at any convenient time. But, the submission of knowledge should be carried out in stages, in accordance with educational standards, coordinated by the educational system and managed by English teachers. It is the teacher who is obliged to activate the potential of the student, his knowledge base and personality, make him an independent unit of the teaching system and direct him to the new peaks of knowledge.

The current trend in teaching foreign languages is to switch to a personally oriented education system, which, as a subsystem, should contain a student. All these requirements, like no other direction, meet the distance learning of the English language, using Internet technology, since it is it that fully implements the right to free access to information for each of the participants in the educational process.

Distance learning, incorporating all the latest developments in the education system, opens up wide prospects for school education. However, the importance of distance learning of foreign languages in the general secondary education system becomes quite serious only if it is connected with other educational means, such as printed materials and multimedia equipment. Teachers of foreign languages, in particular English, as information carriers, should not only transfer their own knowledge to students and activate each of the components of the training system, but also reproduce the content of training courses in such a way that each of them can perceive, understand and systematize the knowledge received. The original information system must be broken down into parts, between which relations are defined and all this is recreated in the minds of students. In addition, this should be done in such a way as to prevent the loss of previously acquired knowledge and skills.

CONCLUSION

Distance learning of English through Skype. In connection with the further development of electronic technologies, distance learning has received new opportunities. After all, by conducting foreign language training in Skype, you can give students the opportunity to master it in a short time. Sometimes the

distance between the teacher and the student can reach several thousands of kilometers, but it doesn't matter. The teacher is able to adjust the pronunciation of words, the construction of structures in sentences, as well as provide any other recommendations on the teaching methodology than if he were in the same room as the student and the cost, while remaining accessible to the vast majority of residents of the Russian Federation. Therefore, it is worth taking advantage of all the advantages that can be gained by learning English using Skype from a teacher with a sufficiently high qualification.

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